

Predicting Cardiovascular Diseases with Classical and Quantum Machine Learning

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Abstract

The recent advances in artificial intelligence beg the question, how efficient are these models and how far away are we from a world dominated solely by artificial intelligence? In addition, quantum computing, a little-known but potentially revolutionary field of computer science, is also advancing at a startling rate. In this study, the abilities and limitations of these two revolutionary technologies were tested, in the field of cardiology. Multiple classical machine learning models and quantum machine learning algorithms were tasked with predicting one's risk of developing cardiovascular disease given their age, gender, chest pain type, systolic blood pressure, serum cholesterol, fasting blood pressure, resting ECG results, maximum heart rate achieved, the presence or absence of exercise-induced angina, amount of ST segment depression observed, and the patient's peak ST segment slope. It was hypothesized that the classical models would outperform their quantum counterparts due to a greater amount of research conducted. To solidify or falsify this hypothesis, a dataset was found, and three classical models (a neural network, a support vector machine, and a random forest classifier) were created using the Python programming language. Furthermore, three quantum machine learning models (two variational quantum classifiers and one neural network) were created using the Qiskit library. The F1 scores and runtimes were tracked along with the raw accuracy of the models, and the data proved that the classical models did indeed outperform their quantum equivalents. These results proved that although quantum computing appears promising, more research needs to be conducted for these models to truly be reliable and surpass classical models in quality.

1 Introduction

In recent years, artificial intelligence has plunged deep into mainstream culture. Hailed as the next step of the technological revolution, it has become a sector of great interest to other disciplines as it can be used to great effect in other fields. However, unbeknownst to the multitudes of society, a new technology has been developing with even more potential to change computing forever as we know it, quantum computers. Quantum computers are revolutionary because they are developed off of the very new field of quantum physics and

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quantum mechanics, allowing them to bypass traditional computing power limits present in classical computers. The first step to creating accurate machine-learning models is to find a balanced dataset. A common issue that plagues machine learning models is that they can be biased. This happens because the data that the model was trained on may have been contaminated with human biases, and since the model only predicts based on the data, it will also have this bias (Nelson, 2019). The only way this issue can be prevented is by using a balanced dataset, to train the model. The classical machine learning architectures that were used for this project were a multilayer perceptron neural network (MLP), a support vector machine (SVM), and a random forest classifier (RFC). What all of these models have in common is their ability to learn from data and predict future outcomes. An MLP learns using multiple neurons (the smallest unit in a neural network), which work together to form an output from a given input. An SVM examines the training data to find a hyperplane that can separate the different classes of data (Support Vector Machine (SVM) Algorithm, n.d.). The SVM then optimizes this hyperplane to allow it to predict future outcomes (Support Vector Machine (SVM) Algorithm, n.d.). Finally, an RFC uses multiple decision trees to come up with a single output (What is Random Forest?, n.d.). Quantum machine learning models can use the powers of quantum mechanics to significantly speed up computing power. Regular computers use bits, the smallest unit of storage in a computer. However, a qubit can use different properties of quantum physics, which cause it to work faster than a regular bit (Flöther et al., 2020). An example of this is quantum entanglement, in which two different entities, perhaps particles, cannot be distinguished from each other (“Entanglement” n.d.). This shows that quantum computers have many unique properties that can be used to create a completely different computer from what has been made before. It is hypothesized that quantum computing may increase the speed and perhaps the accuracy of the model. The two types of quantum machine learning models that were used for this project were the Variational Quantum Classifier (VQC) and the Quantum Neural Network. A VQC is a quantum circuit that contains a feature map, and an ansatz. An ansatz is a parameterized quantum circuit that is used to create a neural network classifier. A VQC is by far the most useful and popular quantum machine learning model. A quantum neural network is similar, although it directly creates a neural network using a sampler or estimator primitive rather than using ansatzes and feature maps. The dependent variables that were used were the accuracy, F1 score, and runtime of the models. The accuracy of the model was measured simply based on the number of correct answers divided by the number of total “questions”, or instances of the data. The runtime of the models was measured using Python’s time library, which returns the amount of time passed for the program to run. Finally, the F1 score is a more advanced version of accuracy; it measures the reliability of the model, taking both false positives and false negatives into account. It is calculated by using the harmonic mean of the precision.¹ and recall.² using the following formula where TP represents the true positives, FP represents the false positives, and FN represents the false negatives:

$$F_1 = \frac{TP}{TP + 0.5(FP + FN)} \quad (1)$$

¹The term precision, as relating to machine learning, is a measure of the number of true positives divided by the number of true positives and false positives

²The term recall describes the number of true positives divided by the number of true positives and false negatives

The purpose of this project was to explore the abilities and limits of different types of classical and quantum machine learning models to better our understanding of these new technologies and to figure out whether these machine learning models can be used in the near future to help with diagnosing patients. It was hypothesized that the classical machine learning models would outperform the quantum machine learning models since more research has been conducted regarding classical machine learning models. Thus, there is more data available to optimize and fine-tune the classical models compared to the quantum models.

2 Methods

To conduct this research, it was decided to create and evaluate a multitude of different machine learning models, all with varying architectures in place based on classical computer architecture and quantum computer architecture. The first step of the procedure was to acquire a dataset on which to train the machine learning models. To evaluate the quality of a dataset, multiple factors were taken into consideration. Some of the most important ones include size, which refers to the amount of entries in the dataset, balance, which refers to the proportions of one label in a dataset to another, quality of labels, which refers to how accurate each entry in a dataset is labeled, and finally noise, which refers to the amount of random or irrelevant entries in the dataset that will need to be cleaned. After careful evaluation, a free and anonymous dataset.³ hosted on a platform called Kaggle was settled upon. It was based on eleven clinical features for predicting heart disease events. This dataset was of exceptional quality and rated to be 10.0 on a 10-point scale for the condition of entries. It contained a multitude of different symptoms and some demographic data which could be used to evaluate with a high degree of probability if one had heart disease. To most effectively perform operations on it, the data was converted into CSV format.⁴ Once the dataset was located, the next course of action was to start developing the different neural networks and evaluate their quality. The first section was the classical section where all the neural networks were based on classical computers. Because this problem was fundamentally binary in that the outcome could only be positive or negative, three different architectures were settled upon for the neural networks: a support vector machine (SVM), a random forest architecture, and a simple feed-forward neural network. These models were selected because they were very good with the specific task of binary classification which is what was required as the neural network would output if one had a cardiovascular disease or not. All of the code for these can be found in the Github Repository.⁵ for this project. An SVM essentially strives to find a hyperplane that separates some data into two parts that are as distinct as possible. They are good because they tend to be fairly memory efficient thus not as resource intensive, and they typically do not overfit as easily as some other models because of a regularization parameter.⁶ which helps them avoid this. Random Forest Networks are another good choice for this task. Random Forests utilize a series of smaller decision trees which are evaluated and then used to create a final value which is then returned as the prediction. Random Forests are also fairly well suited against overfitting because they

³<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/fedesoriano/heart-failure-prediction/data>

⁴A CSV format is one where data in the form of text is stored using comma-separated values

⁵<https://github.com/Glitchez-1984/CSW-Research-Project>

⁶A component of the algorithm which prevents the model from overfitting by kind of reducing the model's complexity.

take multiple decision trees as opposed to just one normally used which allows them to have less error in general. They are also capable of working with incomplete datasets and will autofill missing values with something similar that was found previously. The final classical network was the feedforward network. This network doesn't necessarily have any fancy features that distinguish it from the rest like the previous networks, however, it is one of the most fundamental networks used for binary classification and is the base for many other more advanced structures. Because of its overall simplicity, it allows for a greater degree of personal customization for specific tasks which can turn out to be very useful. The feedforward is simply multiple layers of nodes that feature biases and weights for data to flow through them. The final column of nodes is called the output nodes and depending on which node the data ends up with, the final prediction will be based on it. Since there are only two options in this experiment, sick and not sick, there will only be two output nodes. The specific benefits of the models laid out previously make them very useful for binary classification so that is why they were chosen. It was decided that the programming language used to create these neural networks would be Python along with the model PyTorch, a free and open-source tool often used in high-grade environments to create robust artificial intelligence systems. Once each of these architectures had been created, the dataset was split into a proportion roughly equal to 8:2 with 80% of the data going into training the neural network. This was done by inputting the data of each entry point into the network and also displaying the label for that particular data point, such as heart disease or no heart disease. The neural network would then adjust itself to account for this. The program was run for 50 epochs, or essentially the data was fed into the neural network 50 times with a learning rate of 0.01 which indicates the pace at which a neural network updates or learns the values of a parameter estimate. Finally, after the neural network finishes training, the remaining 20% of the data would be fed into it except this time without any label and it was the neural network's task to determine which label should be used for each entry point. As the model finished training, the accuracy of the model was evaluated based on how many data points it evaluated correctly in the testing portion of the dataset and the time it took for the model to evaluate was also recorded alongside the F1 score, as described previously. Each model was run 3 times and the average time, accuracy, and F1 score were used in the final evaluation of the models. The next section was the quantum neural networks. To be consistent with the parameters, the same dataset was used to train these neural networks alongside the same epoch and learning rate parameters. The 3 model architectures used in this scenario were Quantum Neural Networks (QNN), Variational Quantum Classifier (VQC), and a decomposed VQC. They were all created using IBM's Qiskit library which is a custom-developed Python module to program specifically IBM's quantum computers and to simulate them on normal computers. The first model we used, a VQC, is known as a hybrid model because it uses concepts from the classical and quantum worlds to evaluate problems. This was selected because VQCs often take the least time to finish running and are not too complex allowing for more accurate evaluation of data. Also because they are considered to be hybrid models, similar parameters for evaluation could be used in the same context which would allow for better experiment analysis. A decomposed VQC differs from a normal one only in its complexity as it is specifically made less complex to fit modern quantum hardware which is still very new and fairly weak to work on. We wanted to measure how much of a difference in performance there would end up being. VQCs in general were used more because of their efficiency on current quantum hardware as opposed to the best structure for this specific experiment as we could not afford to use

too much power when running the programs. VQCs are also excellent because they are known to be more robust and protected against noise and the errors it might cause, and because they can be easily scaled to work with a number of different qubits which again was very desirable as we were working with very limited resources. The final structure that was used for quantum computing was the QNN. It once again combines ideas from quantum and classical computing. However, whereas a VQC is more of a circuit rather than a true machine learning algorithm, a QNN fully uses the neural network structure hence the name. It first encodes the data to a quantum state from a classical one which would include only 0s and 1s, and then passes the data through a multitude of quantum circuits which are analogous to layers in classical networks. Because of the quantum origins and because it is not as simple as a VQC, a QNN has more potential for accuracy and speed in theory. It could leverage quantum features such as faster computing and allowing processes to run in parallel as opposed to one by one. However because again, quantum is still an emerging field, this is still purely theoretical. It was particularly difficult to evaluate these neural networks as they required careful and complex formatting of data in a way that a quantum computer or quantum computer simulator could read. They also took a very long time to train with the range varying from a few hours to a day or so. As mentioned above, IBM Quantum was used as they provided free, albeit very weak quantum computers to run programs on. The same metrics were used here once again to evaluate the quantum computers with each model being executed 3 times once again and the average of each model's 3 executions taken as the final value.

3 Results

Figure 1: Average Accuracy for Classical vs Quantum Models

Accuracy (%) vs. Quantum Networks

Figure 2: Average accuracy vs decomposed and non-decomposed VQC

Classical Neural Network , Random Forest and SVM Testing Accuracy (%)

Figure 3: Classical Models' Accuracy (%)

Classical Neural Network , Random Forest and SVM f1 scores

Figure 4: Classical Models' F1 Scores.

Classical Neural Network, Random Forest, and SVM Runtimes (seconds)

Figure 5: Classical Models' Runtimes (seconds)

Figure 6: Quantum vs Classical Machine Learning Models in Terms of Accuracy

Average F1 for Classical and Quantum models

Figure 7: Average F1 Score for Classical vs Quantum Models

4 Discussion

According to the data, the classical neural network models were significantly more accurate than the quantum neural networks. In addition, they also had a higher F1 score and a lower runtime, making them much more optimal than their quantum counterparts. Figure 1 shows that the classical models, on average, scored 28.91% higher than the quantum models. In addition, Figure 6 shows that both neural networks did better than the others in their respective categories. The classical neural network outperformed the classical SVM and RFC by 2.82 and 3.9% respectively. Regarding computational efficiency, the Support Vector Machine (SVM) displayed a notably superior runtime compared to other classical models, as evidenced in Figure 5. This enhanced performance was not at the expense of accuracy or F1 score, with the SVM paralleling the Random Forest Classifier (RFC) in these metrics. Notably, the SVM's accuracy exceeded the RFC by 1.08%, as indicated in Figure 3, and its F1 score was marginally higher by 0.00798, as shown in Figure 4. In terms of runtime, the SVM significantly outperformed the RFC, with only 11.89 seconds compared to the RFC's 38.76 seconds, suggesting the SVM's greater efficiency. In the realm of quantum models, Figure 2 shows that the non-decomposed Variational Quantum Classifier (VQC) surpassed its decomposed variant by 2.7448%, while the Quantum Neural Network (QNN) outscored the non-decomposed VQC by 4.0662%, marking it as the most effective quantum model. Figure 7 displays the disparity between classical and quantum models in F1 score terms. On average, classical models attained an F1 score of 0.90134, outshining the quantum models' average of 0.5476. This data indicates that classical models, overall, surpass their quantum counterparts in terms of accuracy, F1 score, and runtime. This data proves that classical machine learning models, while they may be surpassed in the future, are still currently superior to their quantum counterparts. However, it is safe to say that machine learning still cannot be trusted to replace

doctors. Although an 89-91% accuracy is considered to be a decent accuracy, when put into real-world applications, especially medicine, is unacceptable. 89-91% accuracy implies that if there were 100,000 participants who either had or didn't have cardiovascular disease, the model would only predict 89,000 - 91,000 correctly. This means that it would misdiagnose 9,000 - 11,000 people. Therefore, it may be more advantageous to have a hybrid diagnosing system with both the machine learning model and a skilled cardiologist. Compared to previous findings, the results of this study appear to be contradictory to those conducted by other researchers. In the SMU Data Science Review, researchers Havenstein, Thomas, and Chandrasekaran found that a quantum SVM outperformed a classical SVM by 10% accuracy for the Breast Cancer dataset, a common dataset used for machine learning (Havenstein et al 2023). These researchers also utilized IBM Quantum, although they utilized the Statevector simulator and the IBMQX4, which is a five-qubit quantum computer (Havenstein et al 2023). One of the main issues that was faced while trying to test the quantum models for this research project was the issue of computing power. Despite having IBM Quantum, the VQCs for this project required eleven qubits, while IBM's free quantum computer only had seven. As a result, the VQC needed to be decomposed to speed up the processing of the program. This is a major reason why the accuracy of the VQCs and QNN were lower than the hypothesized results as well as the results shown in the SMU Data Science Review experiments. One major error of the project was not having a proper simulator to run the quantum machine learning models. This skewed the results and caused the accuracy to drop significantly. With a stronger quantum computer at hand, it is hypothesized that the quantum model would perform at close to the same level as the classical models. A way to correct this error would be to find a way to gain access to a simulator or a more powerful quantum computer. One way this study could be expanded is by examining different types of optimization algorithms and their impacts on the machine learning models' performance. If this experiment considered optimization algorithms, then the results would provide the absolute optimal configurations for both the type of machine learning model and the most optimal way to configure the network. This would create a conclusive study regarding not only which machine learning model is best, but also which optimization algorithm to use for the model. Finally, if the study were extended to multiple fields, rather than just cardiovascular disease, a broader spectrum of tasks could be used to determine the advantages and disadvantages of using classical vs quantum models.

5 Conclusion

The comparative study between classical and quantum machine learning models in cardiology has yielded insightful results. Consistent with our hypothesis, classical models—the multilayer perceptron neural network, support vector machine, and random forest classifier—outperformed their quantum counterparts in terms of accuracy, F1 score, and runtime efficiency. Despite the theoretical advantages that quantum models might hold, they are currently in their infancy, as evidenced by the variational quantum classifiers and the quantum neural network's underwhelming performance. This gap highlights the immaturity of quantum computing for such complex tasks and reinforces the notion that significant advancements in quantum algorithms and hardware are required before they can compete with established classical machine learning techniques. The findings of this study not only validate the current reliability of classical models in clinical predictive an-

alytics but also pave the way for future research that may eventually leverage the unique capabilities of quantum computing in the field of medicine.

References

- [1] EPiQC. (n.d.). *Entanglement*. Retrieved May 3, 2023, from <https://www.epiqc.cs.uchicago.edu/resources-entanglement>
- [2] Flother, F., Murphy, J., RN, FACMI, FAAN, Murtha, J., & Sow, D. (2020). *Exploring quantum computing use cases for healthcare*. Retrieved from <https://www.ibm.com/downloads/cas/8QDGKDZJ>
- [3] GeeksforGeeks. (n.d.). *Support Vector Machine (SVM) Algorithm*. Retrieved November 5, 2023, from <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/support-vector-machine-algorithm/>
- [4] Havenstein, C., Thomas, D., & Chandrasekaran, S. (2023). Comparisons of Performance between Quantum and Classical Machine Learning. *SMU Scholar*, 1(4), 11-17.
- [5] IBM. (n.d.). *What is Random Forest?*. Retrieved November 5, 2023, from <https://www.ibm.com/topics/random-forest>
- [6] Nelson, G. S. (2019, July 1). Bias in artificial intelligence. *North Carolina Medical Journal*, 80(4), 220-222. <https://doi.org/10.18043/ncm.80.4.220>